

Digital tools and health

Veillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

We define health as anything related to mental and physical wellbeing, health conditions, exercise, food and diet, pain.

Do you use apps, social media or websites for your health? Oui Non

Which social media platform/site (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Tiktok, Snapchat) is your favourite to use for your health? And what do you like about it? _____

For searching health information, which app, social media or website do you use ? _____

For discussing health topics with other people online, which app, social media or website do you use ? _____

Have advertisements ever made you want to buy a food product? Oui Non

Which foods ? _____

In which media ? Television Radio Internet Newspapers/ magazines In-city display Movie theater Other

Did you buy them? Oui Non

To search for information in general, which media do you use the most? Television Newspapers Internet Books and dictionaries Other

In your daily life, do you ever look for information related to food? Oui Non

What kind of information? On the type of food About a recipe About health About the shops distributing the product Other

Have you ever received information on healthy eating habits? Oui Non

Who did you receive them from?

- Family
- School
- Medias
- Doctors, nurses
- Other

Have you considered them in your eating habits?

- Oui
- Non

How are your food choices guided?

- Guided by your parents
- Guided by school
- Guided by friends
- Guided by your taste in food
- Other

Do your family encourage you to eat healthily?

- Oui
- Non

When you are in front of the screens during the day (apart from meals), do you ever eat?

- Oui
- Non

Which foods ?

- Soft drinks
- Salted or sweet biscuits
- Crips
- Candies
- Fruit / vegetables
- Other

Do you ever eat your meals in front of the screen?

- Oui
- Non

How many times a week?

- All days
- 2 or 3 fois times a week
- Once a week
- Rarely

On which types of meals?

- Breakfast
- Lunch
- Collation after school
- Dinner